

Four regional case studies synthesising stakeholder views identified and outlined, meeting end user needs

Deliverable 6.2

Four regional case studies synthesising stakeholder views identified and outlined, meeting end user needs

Deliverable 6.2

How to Cite

Bramley, B., Smanis, T., Urgeghe, A.M., Principe, S.C., Lillis, H., Krause-Jensen, D., Addamo, A.M., Costello M.J. 2024. Four regional case studies synthesising stakeholder views identified and outlined, meeting end user needs. Nord University, *MPA Europe Project Report Deliverable 6.2*, 21 pp. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15311533>

Version: V1.0

Data of release: 30 April 2025

Instrument call: HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-12

Start of the project: 1st January 2023

Duration of the project: 40 months

Co-funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

MPA Europe is co-funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe programme (Grant Agreement: 101059988). UK participants in Horizon Europe Project MPA Europe are supported by UKRI grant numbers 10067934 JNCC and 10069750 SAMS.

Views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect that of the European Union or UK Research and Innovation. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The report represents the most up to date status of the information. Any potential upcoming information may be considered for incorporation in future deliverables to improve the scientific knowledge.

The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), Aarhus University (Denmark), Climazul (Greece), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Ocean University of China (China), and the University of the Ryukyus (Japan). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 6.2 overview

MPA Europe encourages stakeholders to use its resources. To that end, MPA Europe invites stakeholders to propose case studies building on MPA Europe. These case studies are led and conducted by these stakeholders with support as required from MPA Europe. This document presents the outlines of four regional case studies which have been identified and co-designed by stakeholders of the MPA Europe project, and which meet the needs of these stakeholders and their end-users. We anticipate further co-designed case studies proposed by stakeholders may emerge over the remaining period of the project, particularly once project **Deliverable 5.7** (*Online atlas for Marine Spatial Planning*) is available in October. To that end we are in ongoing discussion with a number of stakeholders on additional possible case study concepts.

Introduction

The MPA Europe Work Package (WP) WP6 on Stakeholder Engagement aims to widely socialise the scientific knowledge and tools created by WP2-5 and to solicit feedback from stakeholders on the approaches adopted and tools created by the MPA Europe project. We focus on national authorities and regional organisations in particular, to support them to access MPA Europe’s tools for adopting biodiversity-inclusive and climate-smart marine spatial planning (MSP); for designating optimal, coherent marine protected area (MPA) networks; and for strengthening existing marine protected areas. We also engage with national institutes, NGOs, blue economy actors, sister projects and relevant initiatives to support maximum uptake of MPA Europe’s tools for a wide range of possible use cases.

Methods

The MPA Europe project has no pilot or demonstration sites as “case studies”, since the study area is all of Europe’s seas, instead we have pursued a broad and open engagement approach from the outset, to inform and involve as many stakeholders as possible in the work of MPA Europe. To date we have engaged 177 stakeholders from a range of authorities, sectors and marine regions. A complete list of MPA Europe stakeholders is provided in the Appendix (Table A1).

Through a series of workshops and events, we have sought to inform stakeholders about MPA Europe’s approaches, tools and results; invite stakeholders to provide feedback on these; and invite stakeholders to propose case studies which use MPA Europe’s methods, tools or results. We feel that this “case study co-design process” with stakeholders is more likely to meet real end-user needs, whilst also respecting the UN Ocean Decade principles of “co-designing the science we need for the ocean we want” (IOC-UNESCO, 2021).

We convened online workshops for each of the four European marine regions (North-East Atlantic, Baltic Sea, Black Sea and Mediterranean Sea) in 2023 to introduce the project and answer stakeholders’ questions. We summarised our responses to these questions in a [FAQ’s](#) document which we shared with all stakeholders and added to our website. In 2024 and 2025 we co-convened four hybrid stakeholder workshops, again for each European marine region, in collaboration with related EMFAF and Horizon Europe projects and initiatives (such as [PROTECT BALTIC](#), [MSP-GREEN](#), [MSP4BIO](#), and [MEDIGREEN](#) projects). This was intentional in order to identify and foster synergies between our project and related initiatives and to optimise value for stakeholders from these participatory events. At each event we were joined by our science colleagues to present MPA Europe’s results to date and we invited stakeholders to provide feedback and propose case-studies using the results of MPA Europe. We wrote a report for each workshop summarising the discussions and we shared these with all stakeholders present at the workshops and those stakeholders from the region who were unable to attend (see Figure 1).

We have also participated in several events convened by some of our stakeholders, such as the EU Blue Parks community, Renewables Grid Initiative Ocean Coalition for Energy and Nature and Blue Mission BANOS, enabling us to engage additional stakeholders beyond our own network.

Figure 1. The Stakeholder Workshop reports available in [the Zenodo MPA Europe Community](#) and on the [MPA Europe website](#): [Baltic Sea SWR](#), [Black Sea SWR](#), [the Mediterranean Sea SWR](#). A [North-East Atlantic Stakeholder Workshop](#) report is in preparation.

Case Study Outlines

As a result of our extensive and ongoing engagement efforts we have a number of ongoing case studies under discussion. Four confirmed case studies are summarised in Table 1 below and outlined in the following section. These case study outlines have been written in collaboration with each respective MPA Europe stakeholder.

Table 1. Four regional case studies identified and outlined, meeting end user needs.

Status	Region	Case study title	Status
EMODnet - European Marine Observation and Data Network	All	Inclusion of conservation status of marine habitats in EMODnet	Completed
European Environment Agency	All	Benthic ecosystems: blue carbon	Partially completed
European Commission Joint Research Centre	All	BioMESES: Biophysical assessment of Marine Ecosystem Services in European Seas	Partially completed
ARIES, Artificial Intelligence for Environment and Sustainability	North-East Atlantic, Mediterranean	MSP tool and ecosystem-based management	In progress

Case study #1 with EMODnet – Inclusion of conservation status of marine habitats in EMODnet

The stakeholder and their question of interest

[EMODnet](#), the European Marine Observation and Data Network, is the central repository for European marine in-situ data. For marine habitats, this includes:

1. Habitat maps;
2. Ground-truthing observations; and
3. Predictive habitat models.

In EMODnet users may access these spatial datasets via:

- Map Viewer;
- Direct download via the Product Catalogue; or
- Application programming interface – allowing users to stream the data directly to their desktop.

The International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN) defines eight Red List categories, which were assigned to the European seabed habitats in a report by European Commission *et al.*, (2016) to form the European Red List. Until recently, if a user wanted to produce a map showing the extent of each European Red List category in an area, they would have to access the habitat map (e.g. from EMODnet or their own data holdings) and separately find the table of European Red List categories for marine habitats from the EEA and subsequently join the information together.

As custodians of the EMODnet Seabed Habitats data holdings and a partner in MPA Europe, JNCC identified the opportunity to streamline this process for users, while increasing the visibility of the European Red List categories assigned to Europe's marine habitats by attaching the categories to the habitat layers available via EMODnet, so that the categories are immediately available as part of the habitat dataset, whichever way it is accessed.

Approach, results to date and impact

As part of WP3 the MPA Europe team chose to compile datasets of marine species and habitats of conservation importance in Europe, retrieving information from European policies and other main sources, since this information is crucial for policy-relevant research focusing on marine protected area (MPA) designation (Principe *et al.*, 2024). This will feed the tasks of Prioritisation (WP5), which aim to design (prioritise locations for) MPA networks using a systematic conservation planning approach maximising the coverage of marine biodiversity. For further details on the methods used to compile conservation status, see **Deliverable 3.4** (Principe *et al.*, 2024).

To achieve the aim, the EMODnet team:

1. Prepared look-up tables that will enable us to attribute European Red List categories to any dataset that has been classified as either EUNIS v2007-11, EUNIS v2022 or Annex I of the Habitats Directive.
2. Joined the look-up tables to habitat layers on the EMODnet servers so that the European Red List categories are available as part of the habitat layers provided to the EMODnet Map Viewer and the public facing EMODnet application programming interface.
3. Altered the pop-up boxes on the EMODnet Map Viewer so that the European Red List category appears alongside the habitat type (see Figure 2).
4. Joined the look-up tables to downloadable habitat datasets available via the EMODnet Product Catalogue.

Now this information is embedded within the habitat layers themselves, more attention is drawn to the threats facing many of Europe’s habitats and making the data accessible for marine spatial planning and conservation action.

Figure 2. EMODnet Map Viewer demonstrating that the European Red List category now appears alongside the habitat type in the EMODnet Seabed Habitats.

Case study #2 with European Environment Agency Topic Centre – Benthic ecosystems: blue carbon

The stakeholder and their question of interest

The EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 states that ‘*significant areas of other carbon-rich ecosystems, such as peatlands, grasslands, wetlands, mangroves and seagrass meadows should also be strictly protected.*’ The European Environment Agency (EEA) wishes to understand a) the potential for organic carbon sequestration in seagrass meadows and salt marshes and b) how large a proportion of these habitats are inside the existing network of marine and coastal protected areas in Europe.

Approach, results to date and impact

As part of the EEA’s European Topic Centre “Biodiversity and Ecosystems” the task “Blue carbon in Europe – nature-based solutions” assesses the potential for carbon sequestration in seagrass meadows and saltmarshes in Europe. The task includes a literature survey of organic carbon accumulation rates in these habitats, which benefitted from MPA Europe’s EURO-Carbon database containing blue carbon data across European seafloor habitats. The task also included an assessment of the inclusion of carbon-rich marine/coastal habitats (i.e. seagrass meadows and salt marshes) within the current network of European marine protected areas.

The EEA project conducted a non-systematic literature search, primarily using recent review papers (including some currently under review) and secondary sources, including the [European seagrass and saltmarsh habitats database](#) (Graversen *et al.*, 2024), a sub dataset of the preliminary version EURO-Carbon database developed in the context of MPA Europe as part of **Deliverable 4.1.** and **4.2** (Graversen *et al.*, 2023ab). The sub dataset of sediment organic carbon in vegetated habitats blue carbon was prepared with the support from [OBAMA-NEXT](#), where relevant data had already been synthesised. These were supplemented with additional detailed literature searches and targeted data analyses for seagrass and saltmarsh habitats.

SPATIAL COVERAGE OF BLUE CARBON DATA in European seagrass and saltmarsh habitats

8,870 sample data points

373 sampling sites

6 species
(update Sept 2024)

© Graversen et al (2024) - MPA Europe

Figure 3. Infographic on the MPA Europe database on blue carbon in European seagrass and saltmarsh habitats (Graversen *et al.*, 2024). EEA project benefitted from the seagrass and saltmarsh component of the blue carbon database.

The preliminary results of the EEA blue carbon task are contained in two internal EEA deliverables in 2024 (one on the literature survey, one on a spatial assessment), which will be developed into a publicly accessible EEA report in 2025.

Case study #3 with European Commission Joint Research Centre - BioMESES: Biophysical assessment of Marine Ecosystem Services in European Seas

The stakeholder and their question of interest

The System of Environmental and Economic Accounts - Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA EA) and the Knowledge Innovation Project on Integrated Natural Capital and Ecosystem Services (KIP-INCA) have developed a Guidance note on ecosystem extent accounts (ESTAT, 2023) including an EU-wide methodology. This methodology provides a geospatial ecosystem assessment, considering physical and monetary ecosystem services accounts, which is based only on terrestrial ecosystems.

The Joint Research Centre (JRC) team working with an expert wishes to undertake an [Integrated Natural Capital Accounting](#) (INCA) follow-up on ecosystem services marine accounts, through the biophysical assessment of selected marine ecosystem services. Biophysical assessments are used to quantify ecosystems' capacity to deliver ecosystem services for human benefit and the amount of harvested yield provided by such capacity. This will complete the INCA framework for Europe by providing applications and developing methodologies to fill voluntary accounts concerning marine ecosystem services and support and assist EU Member States with the compilations of ecosystem extent accounts to meet the future reporting obligation (amended Regulation (EU) 691/2011).

The MPA Europe project will assist the JRC team and expert with the biophysical assessment of marine ecosystem services of (i) fish provision (including aquaculture), (ii) nature-based recreation, and (iii) blue carbon and related services at the scale of European seas. In particular, MPA Europe will provide data on marine species distributions gathered under WP3 (Principe *et al.*, 2023) and a pan-European dataset on organic carbon in marine sediments (i.e. EURO-Carbon dataset compiled under WP4 (Lønborg *et al.*, 2025), as well as expertise in marine ecosystem services and marine accounting (see Addamo & La Notte, 2023; Addamo *et al.*, 2025; Addamo *et al.*, *under review*).

Approach, results to date and impact

Biophysical assessments (including technical instructions for their performance) are being undertaken for three marine ecosystem services: nature-based recreation, fish provisioning and blue carbon and related services. In addition, the study will describe the development of sustainable ecological indicators for fish provisioning services.

For nature-based recreation services, a subset of mammal and turtle species' geographic occurrences at the European, marine region and country levels will be gathered from MPA Europe (Principe *et al.*, 2023).

For fish provisioning (including aquaculture) services, a subset of fish species' geographic occurrences at the European, marine region and country levels will be gathered from MPA Europe (Principe *et al.*, 2023), while fishery capture and aquaculture production biomass data will be extracted from the Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO) and based on information reported by countries (see Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF) reports).

For blue carbon and related services, maps of organic carbon concentrations in seabed sediments created by MPA Europe based on its [EURO-Carbon full dataset](#) will be extracted (Lønborg *et al.*, 2025).

Figure 4. MPA Europe maps of sampling points (left) and modelled (right) organic carbon (OC) concentrations in marine sediments that will be used as the main data source for input to the ecosystem services analysis. Please note that this does not represent the final version of the project output.

For the sustainable ecological indicators for fish provisioning services, fishing capture data will be extracted from sources held by FAO, International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) and the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet), reporting information at the European, marine region and country levels.

The preliminary results of the JRC tasks are contained in two internal JRC deliverables in 2024 and 2025, which will be developed into the first pilot case-study of biophysical assessment of marine ecosystem services at European level. The final scientific technical report which will be publicly available in 2026.

Quotation(s) from JRC D3 team or their end-user community:

“JRC will use these EU biophysical accounts for developing monetary accounts to demonstrate the potential of these metrics in support of policy making and for further expanding the development by Member States of ecosystem services accounts on a regular basis, as mandated by [Regulation \(EU\) 2024/3024](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 November 2024 amending [Regulation \(EU\) No 691/2011](#) on European environmental economic accounts as regards introducing new environmental economic account modules.”

Acknowledgements

The acknowledgements include Silas Principe (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, UNESCO), Pieter Provoost (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, UNESCO), Ward Appeltans (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, UNESCO), Anna M Addamo (Nord University, NORD), Mark John Costello (Nord, University, NORD), and Marius Saunders (Statsforvalteren i Nordland) for providing expertise, data on European marine biodiversity and spatial maps produced under the framework of the Horizon Europe Project Marine Protected Areas Europe (MPA Europe, <https://mpa-europe.eu/>, Grant Agreement 101059988). Additional funding: Fee paid expert contract number - CT-EX2024D915807-101

Case study #4 with ARIES, Artificial Intelligence for Environment and Sustainability – MSP Tool and Ecosystem Based Management

The stakeholder and their question of interest

[ARIES, Artificial Intelligence for Environment and Sustainability](#), is an innovative initiative focused on redefining open science by revolutionising data-intensive science for decision-making. The organisation ensures that scientific data and models are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). By developing the first AI-powered Knowledge Commons, ARIES leverages artificial intelligence to advance research and innovation in environmental sustainability. Its mission is to empower stakeholders—from individuals to businesses and governments—to make informed decisions that address pressing environmental and sustainability challenges, ultimately building a more sustainable future for generations to come.

ARIES team focuses on creating a tool to assess marine spatial plans with an ecosystem service perspective and based on future climate change scenarios (test area: Spain). The work is divided into three sections: 1) ecosystem distribution modelling (mainly focusing on saltmarsh) and species biomass evolution (mainly fish stocks) under climate change scenarios; 2) ocean physical stock accounts to track changes in ecosystem extent and condition and link them to ecosystem services; 3) create a GIS tool to integrate all these methodologies, as well as marine economic activities data, to let stakeholders test how ecosystem services will change with climate change scenarios as well as depending where they want to install wind farms.

Approach, results to date and impact

The methodological approach depends on the section described above. Section 1 combines a process-based model with machine learning algorithms to simulate the evolution of saltmarsh ecosystem in different sea level rise scenarios (Egidazu-de la Parte *et al.*, 2025). and to estimate fish stock biomass under future climate change scenarios. Section 2 combines a EUNIS seabed classification system with an ecological valuation method to assess marine physical accounts (i.e. extent and condition). The section 3 methodology still has to be defined. However, the GIS app (focused on Spain) will be a platform that users can use to run the saltmarsh evolution methodology and ocean physical stock accounts methodology.

The methodology planned in the case study will be based on SDMs and data processing pipelines developed in the MPA Europe project. MPA Europe developed a framework for species distribution modelling that generated range maps for over 12,500 species in Europe (Principe *et al.*, 2023). Predictions are available for the current period, and for the future across five different Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP1-SSP5), according to the CMIP6 (Coupled Model Inter-Comparison Project). Models from saltmarsh species can be potentially integrated into the proposed workflow, enabling a better understanding of the future changes in the distribution of this critical ecosystem. Finally, the GIS app dashboard planned under this case study will be created following the structure of the [MPA Europe map platform](#), and other results and methods developed by the MPA Europe project can also be incorporated (e.g. ocean connectivity and ecosystem classification).

The linkage between ARIES and MPA Europe will enable the scalability of methodologies to other European marine areas, as well as the incorporation of additional data sources of species occurrence and abundance (e.g., EUROGOOS, OBIS). The GIS app will be capable of providing various maps and tables of marine physical accounts, depending on the area of interest. MPA Europe's experience with the [MPA Europe map platform](#) will also contribute to the development of the GIS application.

Quotation(s) from ARIES team or their end-user community:

The ARIES team's end-user community includes international organisations (e.g., the United Nations), national governments (e.g., the Spanish government, the Nigerian government), and regional and local governments (e.g., the Basque Country government, the Valencia municipality). Thus, this study case has a great potential to benefit multiple stakeholders globally. In addition to the MPA Europe collaboration, a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) between ARIES and EUROGOOS/OBIS could potentially be signed to further enhance the integration of these data sources into the ARIES models.

Figure 6. The proposed ARIES GIS app will be created following the structure of the [MPA Europe Map Platform](#), where users can explore species and habitats range maps.

Acknowledgements

Fundings relevant to this case study are PRE2022-102042 funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by the María de Maeztu Unit of Excellence 2023-2027 Ref. CEX2021-001201-M, funded by MCIN/AEI /10.13039/501100011033; and by the Basque Government through the BERC 2022-2025 programme. This research is also funded by the European Union Horizon Europe project: MARine Biodiversity and Ecosystem Functioning leading to Ecosystem Services (EC HE - Project 101060937 — MARBEFES – www.marbefes.eu).

Conclusion

The four case studies outlined above range from making the conservation status of species readily accessible to the research community, to mapping the extent of protection of key blue carbon ecosystems such as seagrasses and saltmarsh, to the projection and evaluation of various ecosystem services under different climate change scenarios. These give an indication of the broad utility of MPA Europe's results to date and the potential for further impact from the project. Although one of the main project deliverables, an atlas for marine spatial planning, is yet to come, these case studies demonstrate the usefulness of several of the project's outputs in isolation, such as MPA Europe species distribution models under current and future potential climate conditions, and the new EURO-Carbon database.

Next steps

We are continuing to discuss further potential case uses for MPA Europe's results with a range of different stakeholders and we anticipate new case studies co-designed with stakeholders and meeting end user needs may be outlined before the MPA Europe project ends in April 2026.

References

- Addamo, A.M., & La Notte, A. (2023). Towards an ecosystem-based approach in marine ecosystem accounting. *Seagrass ecosystems in the Mediterranean Sea: from diversity to restoration*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2760/612075>, JRC130756
- Addamo, A.M., La Notte, A., Ferrini, S., & Grilli, G. (2025). Marine ecosystem services of seagrass in physical and monetary terms. The Mediterranean Sea case study. *Ecological Economics* 227:108420. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2024.108420>
- Addamo A.M., La Notte A., Ferrini S., & Grilli G. (*under review*). Indicators for ecosystem services and vulnerabilities in the Mediterranean Sea. An initial application. *Ecological Indicator*
- Egidazu-de la Parte, B., Balbi, S., Villa, F., Bengochea, D., Curcio, A.C., Galván, C., González, C.J., Juanes, J.A., Ondiviela, B., Peralta, G., Puente, A., Ramos, E., Rodríguez-Rojo, C.N., & Pascual, M. (2025). Eco-geomorphic modelling response of tidal marshes to sea level rise and changes in suspended sediment supply. *Science of The Total Environment*, 958, 178164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.178164>
- European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, Rodwell, J., García Criado, M., Gubbay, S., Borg, J., ... & Kennedy, M. (2016). *European red list of habitats. Part 1, Marine habitats*, Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2779/032638>
- Graversen, A.E.L., Lønborg, C., Addamo, A.M., Cordingley, A., Stewart, E., Costello, M.J., & Krause-Jensen D (2023a) Database of estimated carbon storage in European marine biogenic habitats. Nord University, MPA Europe Project Report Deliverable 4.1, 19 pp.
- Graversen, A.E.L., Lønborg, C., Addamo, A.M., Cordingley, A., Stewart, E., Costello, M.J., & Krause-Jensen, D. (2023b) Database of carbon storage in European marine non-biogenic sediment habitats. Nord University, MPA Europe Project Report Deliverable 4.2, 11 pp.
- Graversen, A.E.L., Addamo, A.M., Lønborg, C., Pedersen, S.G., Krause-Jensen, D., ... & Yan Yao, Y. (2024). Database on blue carbon in European seagrass and saltmarsh habitats. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12665612>
- IOC-UNESCO. (2021). *Co-designing the Science We Need for the Ocean We Want: Guidance and Recommendations for Collaborative Approaches to Designing & Implementing Decade Actions*. Paris, UNESCO. (The Ocean Decade Series, 29).
- Lønborg, C., Løvgren Graversen, E., Addamo, A.M., Pedersen, S.G., Chemello, S., Alejo, I., Apostolaki, E., Asplund, M., Austin, W., Berov, D., Berto, D., Bjork, M., Black, K., Bobchev, N., Bonaglia, S., Borgersen, G., Bouma, T., Costello, M.J., Dahl, M., ... & Krause Jensen, D. (2025). EURO-Carbon Full Dataset. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14905489>
- Principe, S.C., Appeltans, W., Provoost, P., Burrows, M., Assis, J., Addamo, A.M., & Costello M.J. (2023). Publish maps and models of species environmental niches and geographic distributions in Europe on OBIS. Nord University, MPA Europe Project Report Deliverable 3.2, 21 pp + Appendix. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10058739>
- Principe, S.C., Lillis, H., Addamo, A.M., Stewart, E., Appeltans, W., Provoost, P., Costello M.J. (2024). Database of species and habitats conservation status. Nord University, MPA Europe Project Report Deliverable 3.4, 38 pp. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11075390>

Appendix

Table A1. List of stakeholders engaged with MPA Europe project ordered by marine region.

No.	Stakeholder type	Organisation	Country	Marine region
1	IGO	DG MARE (MSEG)	Regional	All
2	IGO	DG Environment (MEG)	Regional	All
3	IGO	ICES - WKCCCMSP	Regional	All
4	Sister project (same call)	MSP4Bio	Regional	All
5	Sister project (same call)	Thünen Institute of Sea Fisheries - Marine Plan	Regional	All
6	Sister project	Blue Connect	Regional	All
7	IGO	IOC UNESCO	Regional	All
8	EU institute	European Environment Agency	Regional	All
9	Sister project	Blue Parks (SML)	Regional	All
10	NGO	WWF Brussels	Regional	All
11	NGO	BirdLife	Regional	All
12	Sister project	PREP4BLUE	Regional	All
13	NGO	Oceana	Regional	All
14	NGO	Seas At Risk	Regional	All
15	Trade and NGO body	Renewables Grid Initiative	Regional	All
16	Trade body	BIMCO	Regional	All
17	Trade body	CLIA - Cruise Lines International Association	Regional	All
18	EU body	EIB	Regional	All
19	Agreement	ASCOBANS	Regional	All
20	Certification body	MSC - Marine Stewardship Council	Regional	All
21	NGO	HUB Ocean	Regional	All
22	Trade & innovation body	European Aquaculture Technology & Innovation Platform	Belgium	All
23	Assistance Mechanism	EU MSP Platform	Belgium	All
24	Sister project	Institut Royal des Sciences Naturelles de Belgique	Belgium	Atlantic
25	National authority	Federal public service Health, Food chain security and Environment	Belgium	Atlantic
26	Trade entity	Parkwind	Belgium	Atlantic
27	National authority	Danish Maritime Authority Blue Growth and Maritime Policy	Denmark	Atlantic, Baltic
28	National authority	Ministry of Environment and Energy (MEE)	Denmark	Atlantic, Baltic
29	National authority	Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries of Denmark	Denmark	Atlantic, Baltic
30	Institution	Centre for Blue Governance, Aalborg University	Denmark	Atlantic, Baltic

No.	Stakeholder type	Organisation	Country	Marine region
31	Institution	Aarhus University	Denmark	Atlantic, Baltic
32	NGO	Danish Society for Nature Conservation/Coalition Clean Baltic	Denmark	Atlantic, Baltic
33	NGO	Ocean Institute	Denmark	Atlantic, Baltic
34	NGO	WWF Denmark	Denmark	Atlantic, Baltic
35	Trade entity	Orsted	Denmark	Atlantic, Baltic
36	National authority	French Biodiversity Agency	France	Atlantic, Mediterranean
37	National authority	French Ministry for the Ecological Transition	France	Atlantic, Mediterranean
38	National authority	French Directorate General for Maritime Affairs, Fisheries and Aquaculture	France	Atlantic, Mediterranean
39	NGO	EcoOcéan Institut	France	Atlantic, Mediterranean
40	Institute	SHOM	France	Atlantic, Mediterranean
41	Institute	CEREMA	France	Atlantic, Mediterranean
42	Institute	Criobe (Paris University), French National Scientific Research Center, GES4SEAS	France	Atlantic, Mediterranean
43	National authority	Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency (BSH)	Germany	Atlantic, Baltic
44	National authority	Federal Agency for Nature Conservation	Germany	Atlantic, Baltic
45	NGO	BUND Friends of the Earth Germany	Germany	Atlantic, Baltic
46	Institution	GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre Ocean Research Kiel	Germany	Atlantic, Baltic
47	Institution	Leibniz Institute of Baltic Sea Research	Germany	Atlantic, Baltic
48	Trade entity	BioConsult GmbH & Co. KG	Germany	Atlantic, Baltic
49	Sister project	BioPROTECT project; Marine and Freshwater Research Institute	Iceland	Atlantic
50	NGO	Fair Seas	Ireland	Atlantic
51	National Authority	Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage	Ireland	Atlantic
52	National Authority	National Parks and Wildlife Service	Ireland	Atlantic
53	Trade body	Wind Energy Ireland	Ireland	Atlantic
54	Institution	University of Dublin	Ireland	Atlantic
55	National authority	Ministry for Infrastructure and Water management	Netherlands	Atlantic
56	National authority	Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality	Netherlands	Atlantic
57	Institution	University of Groningen	Netherlands	Atlantic
58	Trade entity	Ebbing Tides	Netherlands	Atlantic
59	IGO	North Sea Commission - Advisor, Marine Resources Group	North Sea	Atlantic
60	Industry group	North Sea Advisory Council	North Sea	Atlantic

No.	Stakeholder type	Organisation	Country	Marine region
61	Local authority	Nordland County authority	Norway	Atlantic
62	NGO	Sabima	Norway	Atlantic
63	National authority	The Norwegian Environment Agency	Norway	Atlantic
64	National authority	Strategy Department	Portugal	Atlantic
65	Institution	MARE-ARNET/University of Lisbon	Portugal	Atlantic
66	National authority	Azores Regional Directorate of Maritime Affairs (DRAM)	Portugal - Azores	Atlantic
67	National authority	Regional Fund for Science and Technology (FRCT)	Portugal - Azores	Atlantic
68	National partnership	Blue Azores Program	Portugal - Azores	Atlantic
69	Institute	Univeristy of Azores	Portugal - Azores	Atlantic
70	National institute	St Andrews University; Scotland Blue Carbon forum	Scotland	Atlantic
71	National authority	Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge	Spain	Atlantic, Mediterranean
72	National authority	Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food	Spain	Atlantic, Mediterranean
73	Institute	Institute of Marine Sciences (ICM-CSIC)	Spain	Atlantic, Mediterranean
74	Institute	IEO	Spain	Atlantic, Mediterranean
75	Association	AEE (Asociación Empresarial Eólica)	Spain	Atlantic, Mediterranean
76	Association	ASOCIACION CHELONIA	Spain	Atlantic, Mediterranean
77	NGO	Eco Union	Spain	Atlantic, Mediterranean
78	NGO	Client Earth	Spain	Atlantic, Mediterranean
79	NGO	Oceana	Spain	Atlantic, Mediterranean
80	NGO	WWF Spain	Spain	Atlantic, Mediterranean
81	NGO	Marilles Foundation	Spain	Atlantic, Mediterranean
82	National authority	Swedish Agency for Marine and Water Management	Sweden	Atlantic, Baltic
83	Institution	Gothenburg Marine Biological Laboratory	Sweden	Atlantic, Baltic
84	Trade entity	Pelagia Nature & Environment	Sweden	Atlantic, Baltic
85	Institution	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	Sweden	Atlantic, Baltic
86	NGO	CCB/Swedish Society for Nature Conservation	Sweden	Atlantic, Baltic
87	Individual	Feral Malmö	Sweden	Atlantic, Baltic
88	Institute	JNCC	UK	Atlantic
89	IGO	OSPAR	Regional	Atlantic
90	Sister project	Blue Mission AA (EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030)	Regional	Atlantic

No.	Stakeholder type	Organisation	Country	Marine region
91	National authority	Metsähallitus Parks & Wildlife Finland	Finland	Baltic
92	National authority	Ministry of the Environment	Finland	Baltic
93	National authority	Finnish Transport Infrastructure Agency	Finland	Baltic
94	Institution	Åbo Akademi	Finland	Baltic
95	Institution	Geological Survey of Finland GTK	Finland	Baltic
96	NGO	Baltic Environmental Forum	Latvia	Baltic
97	Regional body	Kurzeme planning region	Latvia	Baltic
98	National authority	Ministry of Environment	Lithuania	Baltic
99	Institution	Marine Research Institute of Klaipėda University	Lithuania	Baltic
100	Trade entity	Ignitis Renewables	Lithuania	Baltic
101	National authority	Ministry of Environment	Lithuania	Baltic
102	IGO	Helcom	Regional	Baltic
103	Regional body	Baltic Sea Advisory Council Secretariat	Regional	Baltic
104	Sister project	PROTECT BALTIC (see below for partners)	Regional	Baltic
105	National authority	Ministry of Regional Affairs and Agriculture	Estonia	Baltic
106	National authority	Ministry of Climate, Marine Environment Department	Estonia	Baltic
107	NGO	Estonian Fund for Nature	Estonia	Baltic
108	National authority	Enterprise Estonia	Estonia	Baltic
109	NGO network	Estonian Water Association (belonging into CCB and GWP CEE)	Estonia	Baltic
110	National authority	Government of Åland	Finland	Baltic
111	National authority	Ministry of Smart Administration and Regional Development	Latvia	Baltic
112	National authority	State Environmental Service	Latvia	Baltic
113	Institution	Latvian Institute of Aquatic Ecology	Latvia	Baltic
114	National authority	Ministry of Infrastructure - Maritime Spatial Planning Unit Maritime Economy Department	Poland	Baltic
115	National authority	Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development	Poland	Baltic
116	NGO	WWF Poland	Poland	Baltic
117	NGO	OTOP/BirdLife Poland (Polish Society for Protection of Birds)	Poland	Baltic
118	Trade entity	Port of Gdynia Authority S.A.	Poland	Baltic
119	Regional bank	NEFCO - Nordic Green Bank	Regional	Baltic
120	IGO	VASAB	Regional	Baltic

No.	Stakeholder type	Organisation	Country	Marine region
121	National authority	Ministry of regional development and public works	Bulgaria	Black Sea
122	Institution	Center for Coastal and Marine Studies (CCMS)	Bulgaria	Black Sea
123	National authority	Ministry of Environment and Water	Bulgaria	Black Sea
124	Institution	Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation	Bulgaria	Black Sea
125	Institution	Black Sea Basin Directorate - Varna	Bulgaria	Black Sea
126	National authority	Ministry of Development	Romania	Black Sea
127	Consultancy	ProBiodiversitas SRL	Romania	Black Sea
128	NGO	Mare Nostrum	Romania	Black Sea
129	National authority	Ministry of Environment, Waters and Forests	Romania	Black Sea
130	Institution	Ovidius University / Bucharest university	Romania	Black Sea
131	IGO	Black Sea Economic Cooperation	Turkey	Black Sea
132	IGO	Black Sea Commission	Turkey	Black Sea
133	IGO	UNESCO	Regional	Black Sea
134	IGO	World Bank	Regional	Black Sea
135	Institution	National Institute for Marine Research and Development	Romania	Black Sea
136	Institution	Centre National de Recherche et de Developpement de la Peche et de l'Aquaculture	Algeria	Mediterranean
137	Institution	CNTPP	Algeria	Mediterranean
138	National authority	Croatia Ministry of Physical Planning, Construction and State Assets	Croatia	Mediterranean
139	National authority	Ministry of Environmental Protection and Green Transition	Croatia	Mediterranean
140	NGO	Sunce	Croatia	Mediterranean
141	NGO	Association Biom - BirdLife Croatia	Croatia	Mediterranean
142	National authority	Department of Fisheries and Marine Research	Cyprus	Mediterranean
143	National authority	Ministry of Environment and Energy (MEE)	Greece	Mediterranean
144	National authority	MEE - Dept of Protected Areas and Dept of Biodiversity	Greece	Mediterranean
145	National authority	MEE - Dept of Marine Waters and Coastal Swimming	Greece	Mediterranean
146	National authority	Natural Environment and Climate Change Agency	Greece	Mediterranean
147	Institution	PUSPS	Greece	Mediterranean
148	Institution	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	Greece	Mediterranean
149	National authority	Biodiversity and Conservation Department, Federparchi	Italy	Mediterranean
150	National authority	Ministero delle infrastrutture e dei trasporti	Italy	Mediterranean

No.	Stakeholder type	Organisation	Country	Marine region
151	Institution	CMCC Foundation	Italy	Mediterranean
152	Institute	Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA)	Italy	Mediterranean
153	Institute	CNR-ISMAR	Italy	Mediterranean
154	Institute	CORILA	Italy	Mediterranean
155	Institution	IUAV University of Venice	Italy	Mediterranean
156	Institution	Università degli studi Milano Bicocca	Italy	Mediterranean
157	NGO	MEDREACT Foundation	Italy	Mediterranean
158	MPA	MPA TORRE GUACETO	Italy	Mediterranean
159	National authority	Planning Authority	Malta	Mediterranean
160	National authority	Environment and Resources Authority	Malta	Mediterranean
161	Institute	Monaco Oceanographic Institute	Monaco	Mediterranean
162	Institute	Centre Scientifique de Monaco	Monaco	Mediterranean
163	National authority	Ministry of Natural Resources & Strategic Planning	Slovenia	Mediterranean
164	Institution	University of Sfax	Tunisia	Mediterranean
165	Institution	Mus Alparslan University	Turkey	Mediterranean
166	NGO	MedPAN	Regional	Mediterranean
167	Regional body	IUCN Med	Regional	Mediterranean
168	Regional body	GFCM	Regional	Mediterranean
169	NGO	Global Fishing Watch	Regional	Mediterranean
170	NGO	Blue Marine Foundation	Regional	Mediterranean
171	IGO	Pelagos Sanctuary	Regional	Mediterranean
172	NGO	WWF - Mediterranean Marine Initiative	Regional	Mediterranean
173	IGO	PAPRAC - UNEP MAP Coastal Management Centre	Regional	Mediterranean
174	IGO	SPA RAC - UNEP MAP Special Protected Areas	Regional	Mediterranean
175	Consultancy	The Varda Group	Regional	Mediterranean
176	Regional body	MEDAC (Mediterranean Advisory Council)	Regional	Mediterranean
177	NGO	MedSea Foundation	Regional	Mediterranean

